

How to find publications that used your facility and link them to your NIH Award

1. Find pubs that are already known to be linked in NIH Reporter: <https://reporter.nih.gov/>

Put your grant # in the search box

Click the Publications tab to get a list of all publications that NIH shows are associated with that award.

It is a combination of people who actually cited it, things you linked to the award in your MyNCBI Bibliography ([see below](#)) and things you reported in previous progress reports. You can export the list to Excel.

2. Linking additional publications through MyNCBI:

https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/account/?back_url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov%2Fmyncbi%2F

Sign into MyNCBI by clicking the eRA Commons button. You will need to authenticate through Login.gov.

On the MyNCBI dashboard, click “Manage My Bibliography”:

Time	Database	Type	Term
21-Mar-2022	Books	record	My Bibliography - My NCBI Help
19-Mar-2022	PMC	record	Control of Podocyte and Glomerular ...
16-Mar-2022	PMC	record	Inflammation, Immunity, Fibrosis, a...
16-Mar-2022	PMC	record	The non-canonical mechanism of ER s...
24-Feb-2022	PMC	record	Glomerular Barrier Behaves As an At...
23-Feb-2022	PMC	record	Nanoscopy of bacterial cells immobi...
23-Feb-2022	PMC	record	Imaging Type-III Secretion reveals ...
09-Feb-2022	PMC	record	Spectral unmixing plate reader, hig...
14-Jan-2022	PMC	record	Renal Clearance and Degradation of ...
14-Jan-2022	PMC	record	Hepatic Arterial Infusion of Low-De...

Collection Name	Items	Settings/Sharing	Type
Favorites	edit 9	Private	Standard
Sigma 2017	edit 8	Private	PubMed
LSM880_2019	edit 11	Private	PubMed
S100D021685_AUR1	edit 6	Public	PubMed
S1S100D021685_AUR2	edit 14	Private	PubMed
S1Q1SM880_2020	edit 10	Private	PubMed
TEM-AUR3	edit 17	Private	PubMed

Name	Last Update	Sharing	Type
Katherine Phelps	17-Jan-2015	Private	Old NIH Biosketch

NIH National Library of Medicine National Center for Biotechnology Information

kate.phelps@utsou...

My Bibliography

KATHERINE LUBY-PHELPS's Bibliography 28 2 7 122

My Bibliography Help

MyNCBI linked account

Page 1 of 4

Share your bibliography with this URL: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/myncbi/katherine.luby-phelps.1/bibliography/public/>
Make bibliography private

Manage citations Add citations Filter citations

Search citations Search

13 citations have been linked to your funding and added to your bibliography. Hide all warnings

159 citations, Sort by newest to oldest

<input type="checkbox"/>	Casey CA, Macke AJ, Gough RR, Pachikov AN, Morris ME, Thomes PG, Kubik JL, Holzapfel MS, Petrosyan A. Alcohol-Induced Liver Injury: Down-regulation and Redistribution of Rab3D Results in Atypical Protein Trafficking. Hepatol Commun. 2022 Feb;6(2):374-388. doi: 10.1002/hep4.1811. Epub 2021 Sep 7. PubMed PMID: 34494400; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC8793998.	Public Access Compliance Complete. PMCID: PMC8793998 3 Awards Link dataset
<input type="checkbox"/>	Colon-Caraballo M, Lee N, Nallasamy S, Myers K, Hudson D, Iozzo RV, Mahendroo M. Novel regulatory roles of small leucine-rich proteoglycans in remodeling of the uterine cervix in pregnancy. Matrix Biol. 2022 Jan;105:53-71. doi: 10.1016/j.matbio.2021.11.004. Epub 2021 Dec 1. PubMed PMID: 34863915.	Public Access Compliance Non-compliant. Citation not in NIHMS or PMC. [Edit Status] 1 Award Link dataset
<input type="checkbox"/>	Gok MO, Speer NO, Henne WM, Friedman JR. ER-localized phosphatidylethanolamine synthase plays a conserved role in lipid droplet formation. Mol Biol Cell. 2022 Jan 1;33(1):ar11. doi: 10.1091/mbc.E21-11-0558-T. Epub 2021 Nov 24. PubMed PMID: 34818062; PubMed Central PMCID: PMC8886813.	Public Access Compliance Complete. PMCID: PMC8886813 3 Awards Link dataset

You can add citations From PubMed, From a File or Manually.

+ Add citations

- From PubMed
- From a file
- Manually

10.1038/s41467-021-25635-y Search PubMed

Search Results 1 items

DnaJC7 binds natively folded structural elements in tau to inhibit amyloid formation. Hou Z, et al. Nat Commun. 2021

Page 1

1 item(s) selected Add To My Bibliography

Alternatively, you can send the results of a PubMed search to MyBibliography directly from PubMed:

luby-phelps k Search

Advanced Create alert Create RSS User Guide

Save Email Send to Sorted by: Most recent Display options

72 results

Clipboard Clear selection Page 1 of 8

My Bibliography assemble independently on the mitochondrial inner membrane to assemble independently on the mitochondrial inner membrane by ER contact sites. Luby-Phelps K, Friedman JR. J Biol Chem. 2020;295(11):e202003024. doi: 10.1083/jcb.202003024. PMID: 33053165 Free PMC article.

Cite

Share

Once the citations are in your MyBibliography, you can associate awards with them (Add Award or click on # Awards). Select the relevant award from the list of My awards:

I like to keep all the pubs for a given award in their own collection. To make a collection, you can filter the citations in your MyBibliography by award. Then click “Manage citations > Copy to collection” to create a new collection or copy them to an existing collection. I keep the pubs where I am not a co-author private to prevent them showing up in my actual CV which is public.

Note: To see and work with the collections you need to go back to the MyNCBI dashboard. Your collections are listed in a separate panel ([right middle of the dashboard shown above](#)).

To export to EndNote or Refman from the PubMed interface (not an option in the MyNCBI interface):

1. In the Collections panel on your dashboard, click on the link to a collection. It will display the list of references in the PubMed interface.
2. Select the ones you want to export
3. Send To > Citation Manager to export the list in a format compatible with your reference manager.

To export as a text file in bibliography format from MyNCBI interface (not an option in the PubMed interface):

1. In the Collections panel, click the edit link next to the collection you want to export. It will display the list of references in the MyNCBI interface (clicking the link for the collection will put you back in the PubMed interface which is not what you want here).

My NCBI » Collections > TEM-AUR3 [See all collections](#)

This collection is private ([make it public](#)) | [Edit settings](#) for this collection | Save collection to a [text file](#) | Save collection to a [csv file](#)

Display Settings: Sort by Date

Select: [All](#) [None](#) 2 items selected Page 1 of 1

- 1: [Cancer Photothermal Therapy with ICG-Conjugated Gold Nanoclusters.](#)
Jiang X, Du B, Huang Y, Yu M, Zheng J.
Bioconjug Chem. 2020 May 20;31(5):1522-1528. doi: 10.1021/acs.bioconjchem.0c00172. Epub 2020 May 11.
PubMed [citation] PMID: 32353229 PMCID: PMC8667163
- 2: [Wbox2: A clathrin terminal domain-derived peptide inhibitor of clathrin-mediated endocytosis.](#)
Chen Z, Mino RE, Mettlen M, Michaely P, Bhawe M, Reed DK, Schmid SL.
J Cell Biol. 2020 Sep 7;219(9). pii: e201908189. doi: 10.1083/jcb.201908189.
PubMed [citation] PMID: 32520988 PMCID: PMC7480105

2. Select the references you want to export.
3. Click “Save collection to a text file”.

There is online help, including a YouTube tutorial: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK53595/>